

Teaching' Language Skills with Comics: A Case Study in Adolescent Girl with Deafness

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ABSTRACT: The present study the structured and differentiated teaching of language skills through virtual representation with comics to a deaf high school student according to the pedagogical point of view of [TISIPofSET]. In the work cases it is investigated whether the language teacher can teach a deaf student the text with targeted steps teaching with comprehension exercises of graded difficulty and with learning readiness activities of mental abilities. More specifically the study focuses on teaching through the comic game that is "played" with fixed and moving cards in the personalized dossier which use as a 3D cognitive engine. The methodology of the case study of the deaf student is oriented towards the educational model for disabilities and applicate the pedagogical tool TISIPofSET. According to this, the teacher applies the pedagogical principles that state that it is a Targeted, Individual, Didactically Structured Differentiated, Inclusive, Special Education Program and Training in the secondary for the deaf. With the intervention methodology of special educational needs [SENs] for deafness, the teacher in the secondary class differentiates the events and dialogues between the characters and the comedian, according to the text, individualizing memory and concentration skills so that the student to understand the content of a specific text with the illustrated rendering of the Homeric epic. Results present data from evaluation files of five instructional interventions focusing on visual memory readiness, student imagination, text comprehension, and memorization with differentiated instruction through comic card games. In the conclusions it is noted that interventions in language skills from the neurodevelopmental areas of mental abilities and emotional organization support bilingual differentiated and balanced teaching.

KEY WORDS: Targeted Individually Structured Integrated Special Education Program, [TISIPofSET] deafness, secondary education

INDRODUCTION

The difficulties of teaching language skills to a deaf student are investigated in the philology courses with certain texts and with targeted teaching steps of interventions with comprehension exercises [1]of graded difficulty [2]as well as with learning readiness activities of mental abilities [3]. However, in order to base the teaching methodology, deafness [5]and the factors affecting it are first conceptually defined [6]with analytical reference to the importance of bilingual education [7], which is a powerful tool [8]for total communication. As a means of intervention, the virtual representation " Comics " is used, through which the subject chosen for study and understanding will be taught. More specifically, the work focuses on teaching through the game "comics" that are "played" with fixed and moving cards in the personalized 3D cognitive engine, the dossier [4]. So, the teaching problem is approached with the following open questions.

[a]Special educational need [SENs], due to the disability of Deafness [9]and the possibilities of teaching language skills with Bilingual education [10] in secondary education,

[b]. Theoretical Approaches to Special Education and Training [SET] and the Pedagogical Tool " TISIPof -[SET]" [11].

[c]. Structured, differentiated teaching of language skills "TI- [S]- IPofSET " with comics in the specific philology course of the Iliad and the possibility of teaching from a part of Rhapsody VII of the Iliad through virtual representation "Comics".

[d]. Pedagogical Interventions Integration Program "TISI-[P]- ofSET " [12].

In more detail, reference is made to the special educational needs [SENs] [13]that arise due to the disability of deafness, as well as to the need to introduce bilingual education for the deaf in secondary education through the pedagogical tool " TISIPofSET " .

Then, the conceptually defined term "deafness" and the factors influencing the degree of deafness are analyzed. First, the degree of hearing loss is what determines the percentage of hearing damage the child has suffered and is measured in decibels (db). Therefore,

two categories of deafness are distinguished, partial and total deafness. Based on the Decibel values, two basic categories of damage are approximated, hearing loss and deafness [6]. Hard of hearing is defined as a person who has difficulty understanding speech through the ear, with or without a hearing aid. Deaf is defined as a person who has a disability and cannot understand speech through the ear, with or without a hearing aid [10].

It is noted that the cultivation of bilingual education is a right in the school classroom and is a decisive goal beyond the rich material in the written Greek language. There is also talk of the limited education received by a fairly large percentage of deaf people, especially women. Which is a flagrant violation of the rights of the deaf in every country. Even when education is provided to deaf students, it is certainly inferior to that received by hearing students. According to the Center for Deaf Studies [14] and the Declaration on the Rights of Deaf Children, it is emphasized that every deaf student has the right to bilingual education and advocates the use of sign language as a language of instruction, while at the same time emphasizing the use of written language, as it happens in our country.

Degree of hearing loss and education.

Level deafness:	Degree loss:	Importance for education:
Lightly	25-40 db	Difficulty hearing distant sounds. He will probably need special treatment and speech therapy.
Moderate	40-60 db	Understands conversational speech. He cannot hear the class discussion. He needs hearing aids and speech therapy.
Waist	60-70 db	He needs hearing aids, auditory therapy and persistent speech and language therapy.
Seriously	70-90 db	He hears loud sounds close by. Sometimes he acts as deaf. He needs ongoing special education, hearing aids and speech and language therapy.
Heavy	90+ db	It only perceives loud sounds and vibrations. Relies more on sight than hearing to gain knowledge and experience. He is considered totally deaf.

The teaching methodology takes into account the degree of hearing loss, the level of deafness of the child may be experiencing, as well as the importance of these data in education. From the mild form of deafness to the severe form of deafness, the facts change and with them the way of teaching intervention changes. More specifically, from 25 – 40 db it is difficult for the deaf person to hear sounds from far away, so it is defined as a mild form of deafness and probably needs special treatment and speech therapy. From 40-60 db the deafness is classified as moderate, the person is able to understand speech but may not be able to understand class discussion and needs hearing aids and speech therapy [15]. Moderate deafness is defined as the level of deafness, ranging between 60-70 db , at which the student needs a hearing aid, audio therapy and persistent speech therapy. As a severe form of deafness, it is characterized as being at 79-90 db, in which the person hears loud sounds close by, while sometimes behaving as deaf. She needs continuous special education, a hearing aid and speech therapy. Finally, from 90 db and above hearing loss occurs when the person perceives only loud sounds and vibrations and relies more on vision than hearing to acquire knowledge and experiences. This person is considered totally deaf. Also, the timing of hearing loss is included in the factors when evaluating and teaching children with hearing problems, because it significantly affects the development and education of children. Deafness that is present from birth is called prelingual deafness. Whereas deafness that occurs after the age of 4 to 5 years is called metalinguistic deafness. It is called so, as at this age (4-5 years) the child has basically mastered his mother tongue. It is typical that children with prelingual deafness face very serious difficulties in communication and education. On the contrary, children who experience postlingual deafness, have better development and are educated successfully, if of course there are no other kinds of problems.

According to the teaching methodology of special education and training [SET], the different types of damage that can lead to partial or total hearing loss are observed. Such impairments can be transmission impairments, sensory impairments and perceptual impairments. Reference is also made to the factors from which the auditory damage can originate, which are distinguished into (prenatal, genetic, perinatal, postnatal or even environmental). Finally, reference is made to the difficulty of the deaf or hard of hearing

to hear high-frequency sounds (Hertz), such as the sound of high-pitched trumpets. Particular importance for the Structured Differentiated Teaching TI-[S] -IPofSET is the comic with the help of which the teaching interventions are carried out with some visual conceptual facilitators. As are the protagonists of a textual story. In the integration program of pedagogical interventions TISI-[P]- of SET, the teaching intervention is presented using the virtual representation of comics with the use of which the student will better understand the teaching content and more specifically the part of the rhapsody Z from the Iliad of Homer chosen for teaching.

The disability of deafness affects the learning process. The teaching methodology of the case study of the deaf student is oriented towards the educational model for deafness and uses the pedagogical tool TISI-[P]- of SET. According to this, the teacher applies the pedagogical principles that state that it is a Targeted, Individual, Didactically Structured Differentiated, Inclusive, Special Education and Training Program. The detailed scheme of the pedagogical tool of TISIPofSET, based on the pedagogical principles included in the letters of the acronym as follows:

The letter [T] refers to the theory of pedagogical targeting.

The letter [I] refers to the theory of the pedagogical view of Individuality.

The letter [S] refers to the pedagogical view theory of structured differentiated step-by-step instruction.

The letter [I] refers to the theory of the pedagogical view of Inclusive education.

The letter [P] refers to the theory of the Pedagogical program of interventions.

The letters [SET] refer to the theory of teaching methodology of the TISIPofSET intervention for deafness.

PURPOSE OF STUDY

The teaching methodology in the inclusion classroom serves the purpose of learning language skills in the inclusion section of SET for deaf students. The presentation of the structured and differentiated teaching of the Homeric epic of the Iliad [16] through virtual representation - visual conceptual facilitators in the form of comics, to a deaf student in the middle school inclusion department is studied according to the pedagogical view of TI-[S]- IPofSET for deafness. The paper investigates whether the literature teacher can teach in deaf or student of Rhapsody VII of the Iliad, with targeted teaching steps, with didactic exercises and with learning readiness activities of mental abilities and focuses on teaching bilinguals through the comics game played with fixed and moving cards on the personalized 3D cognitive engine, dossier.

THE TEACHING METHODOLOGY

The teaching methodology is approached with the theory of pedagogical intervention, which is included in the weekly lesson plan. In addition, reference is made to [II] of TISI-[P]- of SET, related to the educational intervention program for deafness. It also refers to the SET teacher's book which can be an essay for a differentiated pedagogy manual.

The theory of pedagogical application according to SET, refers to the Education and Training complex in secondary special class courses [17] in which collaborations and synergies of the multi-phenomenon of deafness are required. SEN resulting from the disability of deafness can be controlled with the development of TISIPofSET, indeed supporting adaptive communication skills by creating interpersonal language relationships and at the same time contributing to the stimulation and participation of students with SEN in learning teaching. According to the Framework for Analytical Programs of Special Education (FAPSE) and the four notebooks were created with learning readiness activities for the students which support. The teaching methodology of language skills for deafness in the secondary takes goals from areas of neurodevelopmental areas of learning readiness, the basic school skills, the social adjustment, the creative activities and the pre-vocational readiness skills [3]. The specific areas include general and sub-modules that constitute specific pedagogical objectives and are broken down into clear teaching objectives with indicative activities as follows:

1) The teaching plan described in the Weekly Schedule of lessons [WSLs] which attended by the deaf student in the inclusion department of special education in secondary and general high school [18] and it is drawn up in accordance with the Theory of Pedagogical Intervention.

2) The educational intervention and the personalized teaching routine is designed with the aim of reducing the uncertainty of language skills and the student [19] anxiety 'communication.

The special education teacher's book supports the spontaneous and experiential activities of learning readiness and promotes school inclusion by proposing in this manual the structured differentiated pedagogy and teaching methodology [12].

The methodology of the case study of the deaf student according to the pedagogical principles of the SET unfolds in five phases and uses the individual tools to record the results of the teaching as part of the interventions of the phases designed and carried out according to the TI-[S]- IPofSET .

Data from the first methodology tool for teaching the teenage girl with deafness: a case study named "Vagelio"

The first phase of T-[I]- SIPofSET includes student-centered empirical observations with an emphasis on the pedagogical view of individuality. Thus, the teenage girl named "Vagelio", age 17 years old in the 1st class' gymnasium and in the 2nd semester according to the linear continuity of the educational interventions which she has received from the kindergarten, is in the 16th semester formal and compulsory education. She is supported in an integration department all previous school years where special education teachers with knowledge of Greek sign language are teaching in accordance with bilingual teaching.

According to the individual history, the type of disability is determined by profound hearing loss and attends in high school , the special Weekly Course Program , in the integration department for deafness. Also, with Basic Skills Checklists (BSCLs) [20], she can hear and recognize sounds using hearing aid. She has trouble distinguishing the topic of conversation of the people around her, but she is aware of the knocks. She can recognize and imitate sounds, recognize music and the rhythm in it. After discussion with her teachers , it was found that she likes to dance, participate in the music and sound games in special inclusion class, and can follow commands she hears live or on the cell phone [6]. As for her participation in the dialogue, she finds it difficult to answer. She knows the names of her classmates, knows the objects, the means of transport and the coins , but she has difficulty recounting events that happened in the past and tells them in her own way. More specifically she can say words and sentences using the verbs in the correct number and tense making frequent mistakes in the correct use of adjectives. It is expressed in front of others, using sign language and lip reading to show affirmative and negative expressions. But she finds it difficult to ask questions about the difficulties which she encounters in the lessons. Vagelio, seems that during most of the hours she attends classes in the integration department with different teachers, she knows and accepts her disability. With the teaching help of the special education teachers, she tries to deal with the communication difficulties, thus finding her basis in the flow of everyday life. She often takes her headphones out of her ears. According to her teachers, she is on medication prescribed by her endocrinologist and psychiatrist for her outbursts of anger. However, it is observed differently that she accepts her self-image better than in previous years, [21] and is quite aware of the issues of deafness [22]. In the family history her parents do not know sign language [15]. She herself uses it in an idiosyncratic way alongside lip-reading.

She gets angry when her classmates don't understand her, who are likely to have difficulties. She exhibits low self-esteem as she does not always accept her failure when writing like a pupils in the fourth grader in the first semester primary. She is little interested in learning, discovering new people or things and knows enough about the environment in which she lives. In the family history also, according to her teachers, she often helps her family pick the olives in the olive groves and does not come to school, sometimes she goes to her father's coffee shop in the village and participates in cleaning their house when asked by her mother. To achieve her goals and learn to live as well as possible with her hearing loss, she works with people in her school and family environment, as well as with people outside her family and school environment. She gets to know her classmates and develops stable friendships [1]. To ensure the maximum possible mental and brain relaxation, she follows a program of relaxation exercises. Vagelio takes a "taxi" to and from school on a daily basis, and has no trouble remembering simple information such as addresses. However, it is difficult for her to give instructions verbally as she does not articulate words correctly, which in many cases makes communication with others very difficult [24].

Data from the Second Methodology Tool T-[I]-SI-[P]-ofSET for Teaching the Adolescent Girl with Deafness: An Informal Pedagogical Assessment

Non-formal pedagogic assessment is recorded in cross-observation charts with Basic Skills Checklists (BSCs), from records for neurodevelopmental areas of learning readiness where Vagelio presents several specific learning disabilities [SpLDs] following her deafness.

More specifically, she has difficulty distinguishing individual meanings in spoken speech and also has difficulty understanding sentences that are spoken quickly. For this reason, in addition to the auditory problem she faces, she is checked for her age-limited vocabulary, based on cross-observations, she often expresses herself like a younger schoolgirl by omitting articles, confusing tenses and persons. There are many times she uses incomplete sentences or has difficulty describing a situation in her own words that someone else told her. Also, in the neurodevelopmental area of learning readiness with an emphasis on psychomotor skills, he is able to perform general mobility movements, as she has no particular motor difficulties. Her basic kinetic "disability" is the flexibility of her right arm and the weakness of that arm in contrast to the excessive strength in her left arm. She has no difficulties in fine motor skills, nor in coordinating her movements.

Table (1) Informal pedagogical assessment (APA) of neurodevelopmental areas of learning readiness

Date: 2022, 30 of May		Student's name: Vagelio		Class: 1st High School, Semester: 2nd, 16th semester according to the linear continuum of bilingual educational interventions that the student has received since kindergarten												
Teaching priority: Comprehend text [mental skills] and negotiate specific learning difficulties [emotional organization].																
Levels (line) of Learning Readiness in the development areas with Basic Skills Checklists																
Listening - Participate in the dialogue	1) Spoken word				2) Psychomotility				3) Mental abilities				Emotional organization			
	second ex. C'Sym-20															
A' ex. 3rd Gym-19																
second ex. 2nd gym-19																
A' ex. Second Gym-17																
second ex. A'Sym-16	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]		
A' ex. 1st Gym-15																
A' ex. 6th Dec-14																
A' ex. In Dim-13																
B' ex. Wed Wed-12	12															
A' ex. Wed Mon-11		11														
B' ex. Wed Wed-10			10													
A' ex. Wed Wed-9				11												
B' ex. 3rd Dec-8					11											
A' ex. 3rd Dec-7						11										
B' ex. B' Dim-6							11									
A' ex. B' Dim-5								11								
B' ex. A' Dim-4									11							
A' ex. A' Dim-3										11						
B' ex. Kindergarten-2											11					
A' ex. Nip-1												11				

The mean average of deviance has found in the 11 semester [green line] so means that Vagelio's skills is in the first semester of fifth primary class, five semester below the line of basis which underline with yellow color demonstrating the 16 semester.

Data from the third methodology tool for teaching the adolescent girl with deafness and instructional priorities.

The intervention objective was formulated following the data obtained from the first and second tools by applying the teaching methodology with the pedagogical tool TISIPofSET. Instructional priorities regarding language skills in literary texts were defined by a series of academic literacy skills. The student Vagelio finds it quite difficult to identify the central idea and the main points of the text, as several times when she reads, she omits or does not use correct punctuation, which makes it quite difficult for her to understand the text who reads, and also she has difficulty memorizing individual information from a text. She reads very slowly and often makes mistakes when reading unfamiliar words. Sometimes it replaces, adds or omits letters and syllables or substitutes similar words. These dissenting observations were also confirmed by the philologist of the integration department who is adding that Vagelio easily gives up trying to understand a text. After these observations, the teaching priority is defined in terms of the subject of reading, in which she faces several difficulties [23]. Based on this evidence, the intervention was targeted which was "comprehension of a text of 15 lines with 12-13 words, with the help of visual concept guides with comic book adaptation" and enriched by learning to "negotiate the difficulties he encounters in oral communication with others at school" [25].

Because the domain of written expression, where specific learning difficulties are recorded in the slow pace of writing, was judged to be important for language skills. When in fact, the texts she produces are short in length and hard to read and the writing resembles that of a girl in the fifth grade, in the second semester of primary school. And especially when the texts she writes contain many grammatical and morphological errors, tonal errors, the words are quoted without leaving spaces between them and she has difficulty choosing the appropriate vocabulary [26].

Data from the fourth teaching methodology tool, individual intervention plan in the inclusion department for the teenage girl with deafness

The individual plan of didactic interventions in the integration department for the adolescent girl with deafness it was described with five targeted steps. These are framed by corresponding exercises of graded difficulty for better understanding of the text with learning readiness activities in language skills with differentiated teaching hardware with mobile and fixed cards. The cards suggest the virtual representation of part of the rhapsody and are described according to the 3D cognitive engine with the dossier.

According to the SET protocols applied to the third methodology tool for teaching language skills to a deaf student with targeted teaching priorities. In other words, data is collected based on the individualized instruction plan where Vagelio learns to "understand a text of 15 lines with 12-13 words, with the help of visual concept guides with a comic adaptation" and learns to negotiate her difficulties in oral communication with others at school." The teaching of language skills is accompanied by pedagogical material created by the ecological adaptation of a simple file turned into a three-dimensional language machine.

Teaching the Iliad with Comics to a Deaf Student: The cards suggest the virtual representation of part of the rhapsody and are described according to the 3D cognitive engine with the dossier - Left Inner Folder

Temporal sentence and the "pizza of time"

Neurodevelopmental areas of learning readiness: mental abilities-working memory

Total communication and Greek sign language

The individual plan of teaching interventions in the inclusion department for the teenage girl with deafness was described with five targeted steps using total communication with: Greek sign language[1], lip reading[2] and visual conceptual facilitators [3].

The table lists the elements of structured and differentiated teaching with an emphasis on language skills.

In the table present the differentiating with the dossier cognitive engine and involves teaching steps structured by analyzing the goal and accompanied by Visual Conceptual Facilitators which represented by fixed and moving cards and they use in text comprehension games.

Targeted steps: Vagelio should learn to	Exercise of graduated difficulty	Learning readiness activities
1st ^{step} : "understand text of 10 lines with 10 words and negotiate the difficulties encountered in oral communication".	Exercise 1. Points to Hector- Visual memory-word "Hector" Exercise 2. Points to Helen - Visual memory - word "Helen "	Bilingual reading games with flashcards adapted from comics-
2nd ^{step} : "understands 11 lines of text with 10-11 words and negotiates difficulties with total communication."	Exercise 1. Shows Hector and Helen in Greek sign language Exercise 2. It shows Hector talking to Helen	Bilingual finger reading games and card games
3rd ^{step} : "comprehends text of 12 lines with 12-13 words, with the help of visual concept guides with comic adaptation and negotiates the difficulties she encounters in oral communication with her teachers."	Exercise 1. He lip- reads the dialogues and points to Hector and Helen. Exercise 2. Reading dialogues - Working memory Exercise 3. He asks when he has questions	Bilingual lip, finger and card reading games implementing bilingual teaching.

<p>4th step : "understands text of 13-15 lines with 12-13 words and negotiates the difficulties she encounters in oral communication with her classmates".</p>	<p>Exercise 1. She waits her turn without getting angry with her classmates. Exercise 2. He lip- reads the dialogues. Exercise 3. He remembers and shows Hector's words to Helen</p>	<p>Bilingual lip, finger and card reading games implementing bilingual teaching.</p>
<p>5th step : "comprehends text of 10-15 lines with 10-13 words, with the help of visual concept guides with a comic adaptation, and negotiates difficulties encountered in oral communication with others at school."</p>	<p>Exercise 1. She waits her turn without getting angry with her classmates. Exercise 2. He lip- reads the dialogues. Exercise 3. He remembers and shows Helen's words to Hector</p>	<p>Bilingual lip, finger and card reading games implementing bilingual teaching.</p>

Description of pedagogical material created by ecological adaptation of a simple dossier turned into a three-dimensional language machine.

On the front cover of the file with velcro are attached mobile cards with the personal data of the deaf student, on the back cover are attached mobile cards with the weekly timetable of her class, the timetable of the literature lessons she attends in a separate small room with a certain spatial integration, in integration department of the high school where it is taught with the bilingual education TISIPOfSET . On the left cover of the folder the TISIPOfSET bilingual special education and language skills teaching are displayed with mobile cards representing the time sentence, the calculation of teaching time with the "pizza of time" and the multisensory instructions listed with the total communication emphasis in the neurodevelopmental areas of learning readiness. The structure of the teaching project with the defined teaching objective is listed on the right cover of the dossier. On the side "ear" of the right inside cover of the file are attached with Velcro mobile cards with visual conceptual facilitators adapted to the text with words, dialogues from the comic. On the lower "ear" of the right inside cover of the file are attached with Velcro mobile cards with visual conceptual facilitators adapted to the verbal expression of feelings.

Data from the Fifth Methodology Tool for Teaching the Adolescent Girl with Deafness

According to the SET protocols applied to the fourth methodology tool for teaching language skills to a deaf student, the ecological adaptation of a simple dossier turned into a three-dimensional language machine is presented. Here favorite objects and toys are used in the differences and speak the emotional language with which she faces her adaptation to the environment and the pedagogical point of view of special education and training.

1st step of teaching intervention: To understand a text of 4 rows of 12 to 13 words with the help of visual conceptual facilitators with the adaptation of comics.

.....negotiate her difficulties in oral communication with her teacher

Activities: Dossier games - comic cards

Exercise: Match the dialogues with the corresponding comic pictures.

The text:

Will your rush bring you death, fateless one? your baby, you don't pity the unfortunate me, who will soon be a widow. I will have no more warmth if you die now, but suffering; and my father and mother are not alive. To me you are, Hector, both mother and father 430 and brother and my strong bedfellow.

This shall not go into battle and be slain because I will die alone, with no support and no protector. It's you - he and mother and father and brother and husband and wife - because my paternal family has been recommended from Achilles.

Hector I do not want you to go to battle. I know that the Achaeans will kill you, leaving me without a husband and no child without a father.

4th step of teaching intervention: To understand a text of 4 lines of 12 to 13 words with the help of visual conceptual facilitators by adapting comics.

.....negotiate her difficulties she encounters in oral communication with classmates

Activities : Games with the Dossier-comic cards

Text:

For all these I care, woman, but the Trojans, the long-veiled women of our country I am ashamed of the war like a coward to flee; and my heart does not want it, for I have learned to be 445 brave and to fight among the first

Exercise: Match the correct dialogue bubble with the appropriate speaker in the pictures below

For all this I care woman for you and for the long-haired maidens of our city and therefore I am ashamed to flee like a coward from the war. I learned to fight on the front lines.

Please! take pity on us and stay here in the safe rear line, to organize the defense of the city at the vulnerable point of the castle.

The evidence is gathered from the differentiations made by the teacher in the events and dialogues between the characters of the comic according to the text. Also, data is gathered from the personalization of mnemonics skills and the concentration of attention of the deaf student in her attempt to learn to understand the content of a specific text with the virtual representation of the Homeric epic. Of particular interest are the objectives collected with the mobile cards aimed at auditory memory, visual memory and working memory according to the booklet with learning readiness activities with an emphasis on mental abilities

STUDY LIMITATIONS

The first limitation is found in the fact that the deaf high school student spends approximately 50% of her active school and teaching time with the teachers in Science, Mathematics and Physical Education, which are also the basic language standards. The second limitation stems from the philologist who teaches Greek Sign Language and the limitations posed by the difficulty of applying total communication in the teaching of language skills. An indicative factor of difficulty seems to be the spontaneous use of lip-reading, sign language and Greek written language in order to avoid overlapping codes that delay the full acquisition of the meaning of the text. The third limitation is found in the fact that written Greek is used adjunctively and priority is given in the teaching of language skills to Greek sign language [16].

RESULTS-CONCLUSIONS

The results present the data from the evaluation files of five teaching interventions [29]. These focused on visual memory readiness, the deaf student's imagination, text comprehension and memorization with differentiated instruction through comic card games. In the conclusions it is noted that interventions in language skills from the neurodevelopmental areas of mental abilities and emotional organization support bilingual differentiated and balanced teaching [30].

The first concluding point comes from the elements of the inclusion class for the deaf in which Vagelio attends and is housed together with the general high school and the teaching of language skills. This means that the deaf student participates in common actions such as the time in the school yard, in common breaks and in common school events and trips that strengthen the culture of school inclusion [30]. It is worth pointing out that there was no problem between hearing and deaf students, despite any communication difficulties. So Vagelio regularly participates in all common activities with the general high school, with visits to museums and participating in environmental activities [32]etc. The teaching staff of the general high school does not know sign language, but the teachers are particularly supportive of the deaf students of the integration department. Their cooperation with the teachers of the deaf classes is impeccable, while at the same time they both take care of the safety, orderly coexistence and cooperation of the hearing and non-hearing students [32]. The school director does not know sign language. However, he supports the inclusion program for the deafness and the efforts of staff who teach in the special class department for deaf students. In any case, he takes care of the smooth operation of both the high school, he directs and the special education and training departments housed there.

The second conclusion point, worth noting comes from the data after relevant conversations with the philologist of the general class which made it clear that Vagelio is hard of hearing from birth and not because of any event. It is worth noting that there is a diagnosis from the Interdisciplinary Assessment, Counseling and Support Centers under the Greek name (KEDASY).

The third conclusion comes from evidence from her family who argued that Vagelio's hearing loss was caused by an external factor, while the experts who looked into the matter concluded that she was born deaf. Vagelio's family does not know sign language and not interest to learn. This point demonstrates that the parents' refusal to accept their daughter's disability and certainly hides a deaf relative in the family tree who is ignored or unreported.

The fourth point comes from the data of the Weekly program of teaching interventions Lesson Plan [WLP] with the TISIPofSET pedagogical tool in the inclusion section with an emphasis on the student with deafness. These focused on specific learning difficulties in language skills, based on neurodevelopmental areas of learning language readiness, that test the deaf student 's imagination, text comprehension and memorization, through visual memory, differentiated instruction and comic card games. In the conclusions it is also noted that the didactic interventions in language skills implemented the bilingual differentiated and balanced teaching with activities from the neurodevelopmental areas of mental abilities and emotional organization .

The fifth point comes from the data collected from the integration training in the department for deaf classroom students in high school. An important concluding point is the fact that the teachers do not use the pedagogical tool TISIPofSET and specifically they ignore the first phase with the data collection protocols with hetero -observations and self-observations as happened with the case of the student with deafness. Also, most general and special education high school teachers are unaware of the second phase" TISIPofSET and the "informal Pedagogical Assessment that illustrates the data with some Special Education and Training protocols and the identification of teaching priorities. The difficulty of drawing up an inclusive teaching intervention plan for a student with deafness according to the third phase of TISIPofSET and targeted steps is also highlighted. The data collected from the fourth phase of TISIPofSET with the differentiated educational intervention with 3D cognitive machines - dossier - was quite encouraging in terms of results. Finally, it is worth noting the difficulty of the philology teacher to carry out the evaluation of the integrated teaching interventions of mental abilities in the philology courses according to the fifth phase of TISIPofSET . Regarding the extension of the present study, it is proposed to extend the investigation of language outcomes by integrating [27]sign language into a diverse curriculum of secondary education [27]. It is worth investigating whether bilingualism enhances the overall rate of learning, increases students' motivation to expand their knowledge.

EXPRESSION OF THANKS

I would like to thank the deaf students who I have taught in schools, the parents who entrusted me with the total communication of their children as well as my students who visited the integration classes that educate students with disabilities such as deafness.

ACRONYMS

1. Framework for Analytical Programs of Special Education (FAPSE)
2. special educational needs [SENs],
3. Special education and training [SET]
4. Specific learning disabilities [SpLDs
5. Targeted Individual Structured Integrated Special Education Education Program [TISIPofSET]
6. Weekly Lesson Plan [WLP]
7. Basic Skills Checklists (BSCLs),

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